

MAPPA: MONITORING AND ANALYSIS OF PLASTIC POLLUTION IN AQUATIC ENVIRONMENTS

Microplastics sampling in water: LENTIC environments

Ver. 1

1. Objectives:

- a) Training and applying a standardized protocol for the identification and quantification of microplastics in freshwater ecosystems
- b) Analysis of the relationship between the presence of microplastics and the climatic variables, geomorphological characteristics, land use, and anthropogenic impact.
- c) Contribute the data obtained to the public, with the aim of facilitating the formulation of policies for plastic pollution mitigation.

2. Schedule

Phase 1 (2023-2024): From December 2023 to March 2024, the first coordinated sampling will be conducted, with one sampling per study site.

Phase 2 (2024-2025): The sampling frequency will be increased to address specific questions derived from the results obtained in the stage 1.

3. Participation and publications

- a) Based on the data collected (including previous data), publications will be carried out in scientific journals. Those who participate in the sampling of one site will be entitled to two **co-authorships**, with an additional (+1 per extra site) for those who contribute to two or more sites. However, we recognize the possible labor difficulties, so this criterion is flexible and open to discussion when necessary.
- b) The **order of merit** will be established alphabetically, with consideration of those who participate in additional activities (analyzing additional samples, data analysis, content creation, etc.) In such circumstances, these additional contributions will be considered in determining the order of authorship.

4. Sampling Protocol Options

- A. Deep sites (> 1 m): plankton net trawling (page 3)
- B. Shallow depth sites and/or with macrophytes: bucket and plankton net (page 6)

4.1. Materials:

- Boat
- Plankton net (pore size < 50 μm) with a cotton bag.
- Flowmeter (recommended).
- Metal bucket (protocol B).
- Three plastic (PVC recommended) or glass containers bottle per study site (sample, replicate, blank/negative).
- GPS (Wikiloc app).
- 5 liters of Milli Q or distilled water per site (Blank sample).
- water to concentrate the sample and clean the net (tap water or from the same waterbody).
- Fridge (up to 2-3 months storage).

4.2. To be considered:

- **Weather/extreme events:** It is recommended to carry out the sampling on calm days, preferably in the early morning, with low wind speed (<20 km/h) and no precipitation. In case of storms, wait at least two days before sampling. In the case of extreme weather events, sampling will be postponed until the situation normalizes.
- **Location:** A sampling point close to the center of the waterbody or in the deepest possible location will be selected. In the presence of urban centers (if any), priority will be given to points close to them.
- **Turbidity:** In situations of high concentration of organic matter, the sampling will be repeated until the desired volume is obtained, preventing the net from clogging.
- **Please, take some pictures to share with the MappA community!**

4.3. Sampling

BLANK/NEGATIVE: 5 liters of Milli Q or distilled water will be filtered using the same sampling net (before survey). Then, the sample will be collected in a plastic or glass container and labelled as "**Blank_1 ddmmyyyy**", indicating the corresponding date (dd/mm/yyyy).

A- Deep sites (> 1 m): PLANKTON NET TRAWLING

Use a plankton net previously cleaned for sampling. Transport it in a cotton bag to avoid contamination by microplastics, especially fibers.

1. Collect a sample of surface water in the pelagic zone (center) using a plankton net by performing a superficial horizontal trawling along a longitudinal transect (Fig. 1). Use a vessel at LOW speed ~ 1 m/s. During the trawl, immerse only 3/4 of the net (Fig. 2); it is recommended to make a mark on the mouth of the net to indicate the section that should remain above the water (See heights (H) indicated in Table 1). If possible, secure the net safely using a stable structure and ensuring it is positioned 1 m away from the vessel (Fig. 1). If not possible, hold the net firmly using the rope. Never perform the trawling behind the vessel.

Figure 1. Correct net trawling for microplastics monitoring.

2. Record the coordinates of the start/end points or the trawling distance using a GPS recorder. If you do not have a GPS device, it is suggested to use the "Wikiloc" application on a cell phone or tablet to record the information.
3. It is recommended to use a flowmeter to calculate the volume of water. This should be secured with ropes and seals below 3/4 of the net, in a central position (Fig. 2). Filter a minimum of 20 m³, according to the necessary time based on the diameter of the net (see examples below). If the net becomes clogged before reaching this volume, conduct multiple samplings until the desired volume is achieved. Record the time of each collection to calculate the filtered partial volume and consolidate all samples for the same site. It is important to note that 3/4 of the net must remain submerged for proper sampling (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Correct position of the plankton net and flowmeter during sampling.

If you do not have a flow meter, calculate the required **trawling distance** according to the net parameters as follows:

$$\text{Distance (m)} = \text{Volume (m}^3\text{)} / \text{Submerged area (m}^2\text{)}$$

Examples:

- Net of 30 cm diameter → ~ 370 meters
- Net of 25cm diameter net → ~ 550 meters

4. Rinse the net from the outside inward (Fig. 3) to concentrate the sample in the collector. Prevent water from entering the mouth of the net (sample contamination).
5. Collect the water sample in a plastic/glass container pre-rinsed with Milli Q (or distilled) water.
6. Label the sample: (SITErep1_ddmmyyyy). Keep refrigerated for short-term (~1-2 months).
7. Repeat sampling (2 replicates, SITErep2_ddmmyyyy). It is mandatory to wash the net carefully between replicates. To facilitate cleaning, immerse the net several times in the body of water with the valve open, then rinse with water from the outside of the net as much as possible. Close the collector valve again after finishing.
8. Take note of any sources of microplastic pollution. Example: boat paint, plastic material used during sampling, clothes (include colors).

Figure 3. Example of how to clean the net with water to concentrate the sample.

Table 1. Estimated height of the plankton net that should remain above the water surface based on the diameter of the net used during the collection of a microplastics sample (3/4 of the net area is submerged).

Net diameter (cm)	Plankton net area (cm ²)	Net area out of water (cm ²)	% surface out of water	Exposed height (cm)
30	706,9	178,4	25,23	9
35	962,1	242,8	25,23	10,5
40	1256,6	317,1	25,23	12
45	1590,4	401,3	25,23	13,5

CAUTION: If the water **is turbid**, there is a possibility of the net becoming clogged and breaking easily. Under such circumstances, it is recommended to perform successive trawls (at low speed) and consolidate the sample.

B- Shallow sites and/or with macrophytes: BUCKET AND PLANKTON NET

1. To optimize the selection of the sampling point, whenever feasible, prioritize reaching the deepest accessible location by employing a small boat or walking. If the bottom material has been resuspended, wait before proceeding with the sample collection process.
2. Using a metal bucket, collect a sample of surface water at a depth of 20 cm in the deepest accessible area of the water body (Fig. 4). Before collecting, calibrate the bucket to an appropriate volume and make a mark for sampling (for example, a volume of 8 liters will require at least 25 collections).
3. Carefully pour the water into the plankton net, ensuring that it does not spill outside the mouth of the net (Fig. 4).
4. Repeat this process as many times as necessary until filtering at least 200 liters of water. If you believe you can filter a larger volume, it is recommended to do so.
5. Rinse the net from the outside inward (Fig. 3) to concentrate the sample in the collector. Avoid letting water enter the mouth of the net.
6. Collect the water sample in a plastic/glass container previously rinsed with Milli-Q water (or distilled water). Label the sample: (SITErep1_ddmmyyyy). Keep refrigerated for short-term analysis.
7. Repeat sampling (replicate, SITErep2_ddmmyyyy). Between replicates, it is mandatory to wash the net carefully. To facilitate cleaning, immerse the net several times in the body of water with the valve open and then rinse with 5 liters of distilled water. Close the collector valve again after finishing.
8. Take note of any potential sources of microplastic contamination. Examples: worn boat paint, plastic materials used during sampling, and clothing (including color).

Figure 4. Procedure to take a water sample with a bucket.

4.4. Metadata

- Geographical coordinates
- Altitude above sea level (m.a.s.l.)
- Depth (Maximum and/or Average)
- Water Body Area
- Waterfront development
- Basin Area
- Length of residence
- Monthly Rainfall
- Average Effluent River Flow
- Percentage of land uses in the basin.
- Population density in the basin
- Distance to the nearest city center
- Distance to roads, recreation centers, etc.
- Presence of sewage or discharges
- Main activities (tourism, fishing, etc.)
- Physicochemical parameters: Chlorophyll-a (Chl-a) concentration, salinity, turbidity, Secchi depth, organic matter concentration (in situ measurements or at least average data from the literature).

5. Other links of interest:

Reference Guides:

GESAMP, 2019

<http://www.gesamp.org/publications/guidelines-for-the-monitoring-and-assessment-of-plastic-litter-in-the-ocean>

Michida et al., 2020 (ver 1.2)

<https://www.env.go.jp/content/000170474.pdf>